

CHILD AND PARENT RELATIONSHIPS IN TOHIR MALIK BOOKS

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Annotation: within a delicate relationship in a family, the relationship at the highest level is the one with the child. The views of the family environment are also reflected in the works of fiction. This article highlights the family relations influenced by such different environments using the example of the works of Tohir Malik.

Keywords: personality traits, family relationships, internal conflicts, crime, immorality, future

The formation of a person's character begins in the family; in particular, a child develops willpower, habits, temperament, behavior, attitude toward the environment, beliefs, and views.

Therefore, without thoroughly studying the conditions for personal development in daily life and the possibilities of influence, it is impossible to discuss the traits of an individual and the factors that shape them. It is known that the family is a form of a social group with a specific structure, possessing socio-historical characteristics. For instance, its members are interconnected through kinship, marriage, shared living conditions, common moral values, and spiritual compatibility.

Every parent who wants their child to have a bright future must dedicate their time and effort to raising their children, who are the great individuals of tomorrow. It would not be an exaggeration to say that every minute spent on a child's development becomes a cornerstone for a prosperous future. If parents fail to pay attention to their children in time and neglect to care about their future, they are bound to live with regret and remorse later on.

Such family relationships are vividly reflected in the works of the talented and sharp-pen writer Tohir Malik. For example, the conversation between Asror and his mother in the novel "Farewell, Childhood" is particularly noteworthy.

Asror stepped back and returned to the kitchen. He shut the balcony door firmly. Turning on the tap, he splashed water onto his face. Suddenly, sensing a presence behind him, he flinched.

It was his mother. She was observing him attentively:

- "What's wrong with you?" she asked, gently stroking Asror's head.
- "I can't sleep," he replied.

"You must be tired. I heard you didn't get much rest at yesterday's wedding. Go lie down. If you can't fall asleep, try counting—by tens or even hundreds. Sooner or later, you'll drift off without noticing," she said.

Asror looked at his mother thoughtfully. He found a certain warmth in her simplicity, then silently returned to his room.

This excerpt reflects the mother's simplicity and her constant concern for her child's well-being. The narrative also suggests her humility and courteous behavior toward her husband, indicating an awareness of her responsibilities within the family.

Psychologists emphasize the importance of positive and respectful interactions among family members, as such environments foster a sense of safety in children, allowing them to express their thoughts and emotions freely. However, despite the warm relationship portrayed between Asror and his mother in "Farewell, Childhood", Asror remains unable to articulate his emotions. The reason lies in the profound internal conflict he experiences following the pivotal event that led him down a path of crime. In Tohir Malik's words, he becomes "a child who has come to a crossroads," and articulating that moment proves to be an overwhelming challenge.

In the renowned work "Shaytanat" by the author, we also witness events related to the relationships between parents and children. The character Manzura embodies the image of a modest, shy, and chaste Uzbek woman of her time, who is obedient to her husband. Manzura's tendency not to interfere in matters unnecessarily and her composed explanations managed to soften even the stern Asadbek.

Their daughter, Zaynab, resembles her mother in modesty but reflects her father in determination, resentment, and decisiveness. This suggests that within a family, a child tends to emulate the character traits of the person they consider their hero. Zaynab spent more time with her mother but admired her father's ability to combine affection with strictness, and thus strives to adopt her father's qualities.

At the conclusion of the work, her covert preparations for revenge, venomous laughter, and eyes burning with fire all evoke the image of Asadbek.

In conclusion, every reader should draw the right lessons from the family relationships depicted in the two works and act in accordance with moral principles in the future. In this way, a generation enlightened by the light of knowledge and awareness will be born and reach maturity in the new Uzbekistan..

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